

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 77

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 77

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 77:0 For the choir director; †according to Jeduthun. A Psalm of Asaph.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 77:1</p> <p style="text-align: right;">לְמִנְצַחַת עַל־יְדִיתוֹן</p>
<p>Psa. 77:1 My voice <i>rises</i> to God, and I will ^acry aloud;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">My voice <i>rises</i> to God, and He will hear me.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">[יְדוּתוֹן] לְאֶסְף מִזְמוֹר : 2</p> <p style="text-align: right;">קוֹלִי אֶל־אֱלֹהִים וְאֶצְעֶקָה</p> <p style="text-align: right;">קוֹלִי אֶל־אֱלֹהִים וְהֶאֱזִין</p>
<p>² In the ^aday of my trouble I sought the Lord;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">^bIn the night my ^chand was stretched out ¹without weariness;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">My soul ^drefused to be comforted.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">אֵלַי : 3 בְּיוֹם צָרָתִי אֲדַנִּי</p> <p style="text-align: right;">דָּרַשְׁתִּי יְדִי אֲלִילָה נִגְרָה</p> <p style="text-align: right;">וְלֹא תָפוּג מֵאַנְהָה הַנַּתָּחַם</p>
<p>³ <i>When</i> I remember God, then I am ^adisturbed;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;"><i>When</i> I ^bsigh, then ^cmy spirit grows faint. ¹Selah.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">נִבְשִׁי : 4 אֶזְכְּרָה אֱלֹהִים</p> <p style="text-align: right;">וְאֶהְמִיָּה אֲשִׁיחָה וְוַתִּתְעַטֶּף</p>
<p>⁴ You have held my eyelids <i>open</i>;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">I am so troubled that I ^acannot speak.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">רוּחִי סָלָה : 5 אֶחֱזֹת שְׁמֵרוֹת</p> <p style="text-align: right;">עֵינַי נִפְעַמְתִּי וְלֹא אֲדַבֵּר : 6</p>
<p>⁵ I have considered the ^adays of old, The years of long ago.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">חֲשַׁבְתִּי יָמִים מִקֶּדֶם שָׁנוֹת</p> <p style="text-align: right;">עוֹלָמִים : 7 אֶזְכְּרָה נִגִּינָתִי</p>
<p>⁶ I will remember my ^asong in the night;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">I ^bwill meditate with my heart, And my spirit ¹ponders:</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">בְּלִילָה עִם־לִבִּי אֲשִׁיחָה</p> <p style="text-align: right;">וַיִּתְפַּשׁ רוּחִי : 8 הֲלֵעוֹלָמִים</p>
<p>Psa. 77:7 Will the Lord ^areject forever?</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">And will He ^bnever be favorable again?</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">יִזְנַח אֲדַנִּי וְלֹא־יִסְיֵף</p> <p style="text-align: right;">לְרִצּוֹת עוֹד : 9 הֲאֶפְס לְנִצַּחַת</p>
<p>⁸ Has His ^alovingkindness ceased forever?</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">Has <i>His</i> ^{1b}promise come to an end ²forever?</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">חֲסִדוֹ נֹאמַר אֲמַר לְדָר וְדָר :</p> <p style="text-align: right;">הַשְׁכַּח חַנּוּת אֵל אִם־קִפְיוֹ 10</p>
<p>⁹ Has God ^aforgotten to be gracious,</p>	

Or has He in anger ¹withdrawn His ^bcompassion? Selah.

¹⁰ Then I said, “It is my ¹grief,
That the ^bright hand of the Most
High has changed.”

Psa. 77:11 I shall remember the “deeds
of ¹the LORD;

Surely I will ^aremember Your
wonders of old.

¹² I will ^ameditate on all Your work
And muse on Your deeds.

¹³ Your way, O God, is ^aholy;
^bWhat God is great like our God?

¹⁴ You are the ^aGod who works
wonders;

You have ^bmade known Your
strength among the peoples.

¹⁵ You have by Your ¹power
^aredeemed Your people,

The sons of Jacob and ^bJoseph.
Selah.

Psa. 77:16 The ^awaters saw You, O
God;

The waters saw You, they were in
anguish;

The deeps also trembled.

¹⁷ The ^aclouds poured out water;
The skies ^bgave forth a sound;
Your ^aarrows ¹flashed here and
there.

¹⁸ The ^asound of Your thunder was in
the whirlwind;

The ^blightnings lit up the world;

The ^cearth trembled and shook.

¹⁹ Your ^away was in the sea
And Your paths in the mighty
waters,

And Your footprints may not be
known.

בְּאַף רַחֲמָיו סָלָה : ¹¹ וַאֲמַר
חַלּוֹתַי הֵיא שְׁנוֹת יָמַי
עַלְיוֹן : ¹² אֲזָכִיר [אֲזָכֹר]
מִעֲלֵי־יָהּ כִּי־אֲזָכְרָהּ
מִקֶּדֶם פְּלִאָה : ¹³ וְהִגִּיתִי
בְּכָל־פִּעֲלֶיהָ וּבַעֲלֵילוֹתֶיהָ
אֲשִׁיחָה : ¹⁴ אֱלֹהִים בַּקֶּדֶשׁ
דִּרְכָהּ מִי־אֵל גָּדוֹל
כְּאֱלֹהִים : ¹⁵ אֶתָּה הָאֵל
עָשִׂה פְלֵא הוֹדַעְתָּ בְּעַמִּים
עֲוֹהָ : ¹⁶ גִּאֲלֹתָ בְּזִרְעֵ עַמֶּךָ
בְּנֵי־יַעֲקֹב וַיּוֹסֶף סָלָה : ¹⁷
רְאוּהָ פַּיִם אֱלֹהִים רְאוּהָ
פַּיִם יַחֲלִילוּ אֶף יִרְגְּזוּ
תַּהֲמוֹת : ¹⁸ זָרְמוּ מַיִם אַעֲבוֹת
קוֹל נִתְּנוּ שִׁחֲקִים אֶף־
חֲצֹצִיף יִתְהַלְּכוּ : ¹⁹ קוֹל
רַעֲמֶה אֲבַגְלִיל הָאֲיִרוֹ
בְּרָקִים תִּבֵּל רִגְזָה וַתִּרְעַשׁ
הָאָרֶץ : ²⁰ בַּיָּם דִּרְכָהּ
וּשְׁבִילֶיהָ [וְ] [שְׁבִילֶיהָ] בְּמַיִם
רַבִּים אֲעַקְבוֹתֶיהָ לֹא נִדְּעוּ :

²⁰

You ^aled Your people like a flock
By the hand of ^bMoses and Aaron.

²¹ נָתַתָּה כְּצֹאן עֵמֶךָ בְּיַד־
מֹשֶׁה וְאַהֲרֹן :

References

Psalm 77:0

[†]1 Chr 16:41

Psalm 77:1

^aPs 3:4; 142:1

Psalm 77:2

¹Lit *and did not grow numb*

^aPs 50:15; 86:7

^bPs 63:6; Is 26:9

^cJob 11:13; Ps 88:9

^dGen 37:35

Psalm 77:3

¹*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 42:5, 11; 43:5

^bPs 55:2; 142:2

^cPs 61:2; 143:4

Psalm 77:4

^aPs 39:9

Psalm 77:5

^aDeut 32:7; Ps 44:1; 143:5; Is 51:9

Psalm 77:6

¹Lit *sought*

^aPs 42:8

^bPs 4:4

Psalm 77:7

^aPs 44:9

^bPs 85:1, 5

Psalm 77:8

¹Lit *word*

²Lit *from generation to generation*

^aPs 89:49

^b2 Pet 3:9

Psalm 77:9

¹Lit *shut up*

^aIs 49:15

^bPs 25:6; 40:11; 51:1

Psalm 77:10

¹Or *infirmity, the years of the right hand of the Most High*

^aPs 31:22; 73:14

^bPs 44:2, 3

Psalm 77:11

¹Heb *YAH*

^aPs 105:5; 143:5

Psalm 77:12

^aPs 145:5

Psalm 77:13

^aPs 63:2; 73:17

^bEx 15:11; Ps 71:19; 86:8

Psalm 77:14

^aPs 72:18

^bPs 106:8

Psalm 77:15

¹Lit *arm*

^aEx 6:6; Deut 9:29; Ps 74:2; 78:42

^bPs 80:1

Psalm 77:16

^aEx 14:21; Ps 114:3; Hab 3:8, 10

Psalm 77:17

¹Lit *went*

^aJudg 5:4

^bPs 68:33

^cPs 18:14

Psalm 77:18

^aPs 18:13; 104:7

^bPs 97:4

Judg 5:4; Ps 18:7

Psalm 77:19

^aIs 51:10; Hab 3:15

Psalm 77:20

^aEx 13:21; 14:19; Ps 78:52; 80:1; Is 63:11-13

^bEx 6:26; Ps 105:26

Targum

Psa. 77:1 For praise; composed by Jeduthun for Asaph; a psalm. ² My voice is [raised] in the presence of the LORD, and I will complain; my voice is [raised] in the presence of God; hear my utterance! ³ In the day of my distress, I sought instruction from the presence of the LORD; the spirit of prophecy rested on me in the night; my eye ran with tears and will not stop; my soul refused to be comforted. ⁴ I will remember God and I will tremble in the presence of the LORD; I will speak, and my spirit will be weary forever. ⁵ You have shut the lids of my eyes; I am smitten, and I will not speak. ⁶ I have counted up the good days which were at the beginning, the good years of long ago. ⁷ I will remember my Psalm in the night; I will speak with the thoughts of my heart, and the mind of my spirit will examine miracles. ⁸ Can the LORD be far off forever, and no longer show favor again? ⁹ Can he have cut off his favor forever? Is the decree of evil complete for all generations? ¹⁰ Can God have forgotten to have pity? Or has he gotten too angry to sustain his compassion forever? ¹¹ And I said, "It is my sickness; they have forgotten the might of the right hand of the Most High." [ANOTHER TARGUM: And I said, "It is my petition, years that he shortened by days."] ¹² I will remember the acts of God, for I will remember your wonders from of old. ¹³ And I meditated on all your good works, and I will speak of the intricacy of your miracles. ¹⁴ O God, because your ways are holy, what God is great like the God of Israel? ¹⁵ You are the God who works wonders; you have made known your might among the peoples. ¹⁶ You have redeemed your people with the strength of your arm, the sons that Jacob sired and whom Joseph fed, forever. ¹⁷ They saw your presence in the midst of the sea, O God; they saw your might by the sea; the Gentiles trembled, even the deeps will be shaken. ¹⁸ The clouds of heaven made water descend, the heights gave voice; also comes the hail, your arrows, and are ablaze. ¹⁹ The sound of your outcry was heard in the sphere; lightning lit up the world, the earth rattled and shook. ²⁰ In the sea of Suph [was] your path, and your highway in the many waters; and the track of your steps were not discerned. ²¹ You guided your people as a flock, by the hand of Moses and Aaron.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm was composed when the Judeans had settled in Babylon. That land was not their homeland, but it started to feel like home. This would have happened as the next generation who never saw Jerusalem and the Holy Temple was born. During this period, there was a time of spiritual slumber. The Psalmist searches through the chronicles of ancient Israeli history to demonstrate that the LORD saved Israel even in their bleakest moments. The LORD promised that a remnant of the community would always survive.

Superscript

To the Sefirah Netzach, who grants victory. Concerning the providences of God's hand. A psalm of Asaf.

Verse two

The Psalmist speaks about compelling people to activate their latent spiritual and moral energy, which is happier and often remains dormant and neglected deep within us. Even in bad times, one should never forget to offer their prays and praise to the LORD.

In the day of my trouble, I have sought my Master, but my hand melted away into the night without ceasing; therefore, my soul refuses to be comforted.

Verse three

When I wish to reflect on God, I become agitated; if I desire to meditate, my spirit enshrouds itself. Meditate on this verse.

Verse eight

The Psalmist questioned whether the mercy and love of God from the Sefirah Chesed was gone forever.

Is the loving-kindness from the Sefirah Chesed at an end forever? Has He laid down the decree for generation upon generation?

Verse nine

Has God ceased to grant favor and, in anger, shut off His compassion? Meditate upon this verse.

Verse fourteen

In this verse, Israel declares that the LORD is the sole, true, and absolute power over everything.

You are the power, O worker of wonders! You have made known to the nations Your invincible might.

Verse twenty

The destructive impact of the pillar of fire and clouds that preceded the parting of the Sea of Reeds (the Red Sea in most Bibles), accomplished by violent earthshaking and thunderstorms, is remembered. The entire story is not retold. Just saying that the LORD led the flock with Moses and Aaron is enough for the reader to recall the event.

Thus You have led Your people like a flock by the hand of Moses and Aaron.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

